

LIMITATIONS IN THE RECOGNITION OF SOUND TRAJECTORIES AS MUSICAL PATTERNS

Blas Payri

Universidad Politécnica de Valencia
bpayri@har.upv.es

ABSTRACT

Spatial movement has been used by composers as a musical parameter (intention), and this paper focus on the reception by the audience of spatial patterns. We present the results of a series of perception experiments where a total of N=118 listeners had to recognize simple rhythm patterns based on the left-right movements of 7 different sound types. The stimuli varied in harmonicity (HNR), temporal intensity variation, spectral distribution, movement continuity and tempo. Listening conditions included stereo loudspeaker open field listening and headphone listening. Results show that globally the recognition is low, considering the simplicity of the pattern recognition task. The factor that most perturbed recognition is the intensity variation, with completely unvarying sounds yielding better results, and this was more important than the listening condition. We conclude that spatial sound movement is not suitable as a composition element for normally complex music, but it can be recognized by untrained listeners using stable sounds and simple patterns.

1. INTRODUCTION

The movement of sound in space is a feature that has been used as soon as allowed by the technology, namely, with the appearance of loudspeakers arrays and their control systems. A famous early piece exploring the use of space is the *Poème électronique* by Varèse created in 1958, with other spatial pieces [13]. Trochimczyk [10] makes a thorough inventory of the multiple uses of spatial sound in electro-acoustic music composition, and cites the intentions of composers when using spatial movements. For instance Xenakis [12] describes the goals when using space: “The composition will thereby be entirely enriched ... both in spatial dimension and in movement. The speeds and accelerations of the movement of the sounds will be realized, including logarithmic or Archimedean spirals in time and geometrically ... [as well as] ordered or disordered sonorous masses, rolling one against the other like waves”. We can see that there was a clear intention of using sound spatial trajectories as an element of the musical language and more recently, the use of space in contemporary music composition and projection has become a widespread musical technique. Composers and music theorists have exposed some ideas to clarify the intention and reception of spatial sound. Sound spatialisation and movement is also a major area in audiovisual sound, particularly with film surround

sound systems but also with plain stereo, and manuals provide some hints of do’s and do not’s when locating and displacing the sounds on screen and around, relating to perception or “in-the-wings” effects in surround sound as theorized by Chion [6]. Videogames and even more sonification systems try to tame spatial movement of sound to convey information and represent spatial data. Sound art works space tends to acquire a more effective role by establishing more direct connections between sounds and the acoustic behaviour of these sounds in a particular environment [4], as oppose to music where the practice of spatialisation remains attached to the idea of sound-source localization and displacement, which is the core topic of the research presented in this paper. The experiments described here try to explore if the use of sound movement can be perceived as a musical element, and if spatial patterns can be recognized.

Sound spatial perception is an area that has received much attention and there is an important set of experimental results [2]. Most experiments deal with source localization rather than movement recognition, and more important, the experiments use very artificial sound stimuli and listening conditions in order to obtain measurable results. Stimuli most often include pure sinewaves and white noise calibrated and stable in time, or chirps that have also very strict conditions on how they are synthesized. These stimuli hardly represent the variety and complexity of the sounds used in actual musical works or in audiovisual productions, and we may not confidently extrapolate the results obtained with calibrated sounds to the real world.

The restrictions on listening conditions are also paramount: most experiments either directly use headphones for hearing the sounds or use anechoic chambers with the listener and the loudspeakers located in very precise positions. For instance, Cheng and Wakefield [5] explain that their “binaural examples have been specifically processed to be listened to over a good pair of headphones. Nonetheless, some of these effects are more successful than others, and we realize that not all listeners may be able to immediately hear the intended spatial effects. Because spatialization effects can be delicate and may vary somewhat from person to person, we suggest listening to each sound example in a quiet environment several times over headphones, closing one’s eyes to better concentrate on the sound.” These listening conditions are very different from the concert room if we consider music, and also from film theaters or other systems of real-life sound projection.

Finally, the patterns to recognize are very limited: if we deal with static sound localization then there are no movement patterns, and the experiments about moving sound use very simple trajectories, essentially a slow progression in a linear and regular way from one point to another, which does not account for the more complex trajectories usually found in music or audiovisual works.

Our goal is then to study sound spatial trajectories perception, comparing the artificial conditions on stimuli and listening conditions with an approximation to the sound types and listening conditions we may encounter in real concerts, even if we need to simplify greatly. For that matter, we need to create sound stimuli that have a richness in spectrum and temporal evolution that may reflect partially real music sounds, and we use therefore sound synthesis and transformation tools that may apply to electro-acoustic sound generation like the GRMtools.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

2.1 Sound spectral and temporal features

An essential question of this research is to study the influence of the spectral and temporal features of the sound on the perception of spatial movement.

We created 7 basic timbres, including:

- 4 synthetic sounds generated with the basic synthesizer of Protools: a pure sine wave, a pure square wave, a pink noise, a mixture of the noise and the square wave
- 3 sounds generated out of recorded sounds (an orchestral soft sound, a voiced vocal sample, and a whispery sound made out of breath) and processed with the Freeze function of the GRMtools, which applies a procedure similar to granular synthesis [7]. These sounds retain the harmonic structure of the original sound although they can last indefinitely in time, and they may have grain and *allure* (temporal amplitude variations) [9]

	Sin.	Sq.	Mix	Nois	Orc	Voc	Brt
Amp SD (dB)	0.00	0.00	0.38	0.70	2.57	3.81	2.04
HNR (dB)	93.7	37.1	4.1	-1.9	7.8	20.4	-3.6
Sp. cent (Hz)	220	478	1390	3488	278	380	4805
Sp. SD (Hz)	1	1032	3195	5346	163	168	3122

Table 1: Amplitude standard deviation in time (dB), harmonicity (harmonics-to-noise ratio, dB), spectral centre of gravity (Hz) and spectral standard deviation (Hz) for the seven basic sounds (sinus, square signal, mix of square and noise, noise, orchestral sound, voiced vocal sound and breath).

We can see in table 1 that the sounds have been generated in such a way that their harmonic samples (sine and square waves, vocal sample), samples including both harmonic and noise components (mix, orchestral sample) and purely noisy sounds (pink noise, breath sample), as can be measured by the Harmonics-to-Noise ratio.

There is also a distribution of temporal amplitude variation as all the synthetic sounds are perfectly stable in time, while all the sampled sounds have variations in time as measured by the Amplitude Standard Deviation.

2.2 Spatial movement patterns

This study focuses on the recognition on spatial movement patterns by listeners, and we decided to choose simple patterns and simple movements, so that the task would be feasible by the listeners without a complex training.

2.2.1 Horizontal plane trajectories

The psychoacoustics of sound spatial perception basically distinguishes three dimensions: the horizontal plane or lateral positions, the elevation or median plane, the distance of the source, and we could add also the source size (Blauert 1997). The human hearing mechanism is more sensitive to sound along the horizontal axis than the vertical axis. Vertical localization depends on subtle filtering of the outer ear and the reflections on the upper part of the body and listeners are not very accurate, and more importantly, perception depends on highly individual corporal differences, which makes listening through headphones very dependent on the actual head and ear shape correspondence between the listener and the recording or filtering device. Distance perception depends on many factors, including the knowledge of the sound spectral characteristics by the listener, the loudness, and the possible reflections.

The human hearing system is well adapted to lateral recognition, thanks to the position of the two ears in the same horizontal plane of the head, which makes it possible and precise both loudspeaker listening and headphone listening. Open field listening uses the differences of the sound arriving to each ear, controlling for the Interaural Time Differences (or more precisely, the interaural phase differences) for lower frequencies, generally below 1500Hz, and the Interaural Level Differences for shorter wavelengths that are affected by the head, usually above 800Hz. Movement types Left-Right movements were applied, using the simple panning feature of Protools. For this exploratory study it was essential to have a robust and easy way to generate the sound stimuli, and we avoided more complex spatial trajectories involving specific software and hardware. Most importantly, L-R movements can be reproduced in any stereophonic system or with any headphones, and we can measure the energy of the sound in the left or right loudspeaker. The goal of the study is to study the perception in close to real conditions, focusing on open field sound reproduction, using real rooms instead of the laboratory conditions of anechoic studios with controlled arrays of loudspeakers and very restrained listeners' positions.

2.2.2 Evolution type of the moving sounds

As we can see in figure 1, the movements were performed from 100% Left to 100% Right.

There were two types of movements: continuous versus discontinuous. In figure 1 we can see the distribution of energy in the left and right channels for a discrete or discontinuous evolution (above) and for a continuous evolution (below). Only the continuous evolution represents a true movement sensation, and the discontinuous evolution has sounds appearing either at one point or the other.

2.2.3 Rhythmic patterns

Figure 1: Amplitude/time representation of the Left and Right channels for the long regular rhythm pattern with a continuous movement (below) and a discontinuous *evolution* (above) for a square signal sound.

The task to be performed by the listeners is the recognition of a pattern, understood as a variation in time. Simple rhythmic patterns are easier to explain to listeners, taking in account that we do not have a clearly established vocabulary for spatial movements. The patterns are formed by the Left-Right movement of the sound. Two simple patterns were created: a regular one (see figure 1) and an accelerated one (see figure 2). These simple patterns are easy to understand by untrained listeners and were used for all listeners.

Figure 2: Amplitude/time representation of the Left and Right channels for the long accelerated rhythm pattern with a continuous movement (below) and a discontinuous *evolution* (above) for a square signal sound.

In addition, we created two more complex patterns, that represented a duple-meter rhythm pattern (figure 3)

and a triple meter rhythm pattern (figure 4) that were represented with a musical notation to the musician listeners as can be seen in figure 4.

Figure 3: Amplitude/time representation of the Left and Right channels for the long duple-meter (above) and triple meter (below) rhythm patterns with a discontinuous *evolution* for a square signal sound.

Figure 4: Musical notation of the 4 rhythm patterns as presented to the group of musician listeners.

2.3 Stimuli combination

The sound material is created by the combination of the 7 basic sound timbres, combined with the 4 rhythmic patterns, each with either a continuous movement or a discontinuous evolution. To create more diversity, we added a tempo factor, reproducing the rhythmic patterns either fast or slow (which represents a duration 1.5 times the duration of the fast version). This represents a total of 112 combinations, or 56 combinations if we consider only the 2 simple rhythmic patterns.

2.4 Recognition task

2.4.1 Listeners

A total of 118 listeners participated, including:

- 52 professionally trained musicians, including 47 students of the Master in Music at UPV (courses 2007-08, 2008-09, and 2009-10) and 5 students of the Higher Conservatory of Castellón, that were later eliminated from the computations as their responses were inconsistent.
- 66 students from the film&TV area at UPV (sound students of the Master in Digital Postproduction and students from the Audiovisual Communication degree programme).

2.4.2 Stimuli

The groups of musicians were presented with stimuli representing the 4 rhythmic patterns in figure 4. From the 112 possible combinations, 56 were chosen, representing all the combinations of 7 sound timbres, 4 rhythm patterns, 2 movement types of continuity. Only one tempo alternative was chosen for each combination, alternating faster and slower versions, in such a way that two different sets of stimuli had the alternating fast or slow version of each stimulus. Each group of musicians listened to a combination or the other.

The groups of audiovisual communication students listened to the 56 combinations available with the 2 simple rhythm patterns.

The order of the stimuli presentation was randomized.

2.4.3 Task

Listeners were instructed to listen to the rhythmic patterns, and some examples of the stimuli were played, and then the instructor explained the rhythmic examples with clapping or beating until the differences were clear.

The listeners responded by circling out the right answer among the possible choices in the printed sheet of paper they were handed out. Listeners were also asked to recognize two elements that are out of the scope of this communication: the nature of the movement (continuous versus discontinuous) and whether they heard pitch changes.

2.4.4 Listening conditions

Figure 5: Schema representing the distribution of listeners across the room, and the distances that were recorded.

The main listening setting we wanted to test was open-field listening in an environment close to real life conditions. We used 4 different classrooms, with a low noise level, and in each a set of stereo loudspeakers was used to reproduce the sound. The listeners were distributed in front of the speakers, and we recorded the position of each listener taking in account the distance to the loud-

speakers line and the lateral deviation from the loudspeakers center axis as represented in figure 5. We also recorded the loudspeaker separation in each listening session.

To be able to compare the influence of the listening condition, several groups of listeners also heard the sounds through headphones connected to the sound card of a computer where the sounds were played. To control the listening conditions, the headphone listening task was also made in groups, using the same headphones for each listener.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Data

The responses of the listeners were processed to create matrices of 0/1 values, having 1 when the answer of the listener corresponded to the correct pattern (correct recognition) and 0 when the listener did not choose the right pattern, either choosing a wrong pattern or indicating that no pattern was heard.

The answers could then be analyzed as such to compare the results of each listener, or they could be processed as scores representing the mean values for a given sound a condition.

3.2 Factors influencing recognition

3.2.1 Factors under study

We studied the influence of every factor by computing a regression analysis using all the factors and then studying the factors that showed a real influence. We used the following factors:

Sound features as measured with Praat (<http://www.fon.hum.uva.nl/praat/>): harmonicity (harmonics-to-noise ratio in dB), intensity variation (standard deviation of the intensity in dB), synthetic nature (sampled versus completely synthetic), spectral center of gravity (Hz), spectral bandwidth (spectrum standard deviation in Hz), skewness. As harmonicity and intensity variation had each three distinct value ranges, we added two extra factors that had three possible values (1,2,3) from completely harmonic to completely noisy, and from completely stable to very unstable in intensity.

Movement features: rhythm pattern complexity, movement continuity (continuous versus discreet)

Listening conditions: headphones versus loudspeakers, and with the loudspeaker settings: distance from the listener to loudspeakers, lateral position of the listener from the loudspeaker axis, and loudspeaker separation and quality.

3.2.2 Regression on the factors

Using the factors previously described, we ran a series of regression analyses to explain the recognition level. We can see the factors in order of importance for all the listening conditions (figure 6) and for the loudspeaker condition which is the main condition under study (figure 7): in these figures we use the Beta value from the regression analysis, which is close in nature to a correlation factor.

Figure 6: Absolute Beta value as extracted from the regression computation using as a variable the pattern recognition scores for the non-musician group (above) and the musician group (below). Only significant factors are displayed.

Figure 7. Loudspeaker Listening Condition: Absolute Beta value as extracted from the regression computation using as a variable the pattern recognition scores for the non-musician group (above) and the musician group (below). Only significant factors are displayed.

A surprising result is that the listening condition is relevant in each case, but is not the factor that explains most of the results, as seen in figure 6. In particular, the variations of intensity and evolution type come first both

for musicians and non musicians, and the fact that sounds are listened through loudspeakers or headphones comes as a third or fourth factor, and even if the loudspeaker condition did involve a lot of different listening positions that were not optimal. We analyze later the influence of listening conditions and movement type, but the factor that is from far the most influential in the four regression analyses is the intensity variation, that is to say, the sound features are more relevant than the movement features, and those are in turn more important than the listening conditions.

3.3 Influence of the sound features

Figure 8: Mean scores (with confidence intervals) of the pattern recognition for each stimuli timbre type. The scores are joined into three groups, labeled according to the temporal intensity variation of the stimuli.

The first analysis concerned the influence of each of the 7 basic sounds we used in the recognition. As can be seen in figure 8, 3 groups clearly appeared, and they corresponded to the level of intensity variation in time of the basic sound. This is the main factor from the sound features, as the harmonicity or other components did not explain the difference in the recognition scores. We retrieve therefore the regression analysis results showing intensity variation as the most important factor.

3.4 Influence of listening conditions

We analyzed the pattern recognition scores depending on the different factors of the sound stimuli and the listening conditions.

We can see in figure 9 that the different basic sound stimuli used have a significant influence on the recognition of spatial movements, but the factor that seems to be really influential is the degree of the temporal variations of the intensity of each sound stimulus, as all the synthetic sounds are completely stable in time and yield the highest recognition scores, where as the sampled sounds have lower scores, and in particular the voice stimulus, which has a higher intensity variability and, correspondingly, a lower recognition score.

Figure 9: Mean recognition score for the rhythm patterns depending on the group of listeners, the listening conditions and the degree of intensity variation. The scale spans from 1 (100% recognition) down to 0 (0% recognition) and the error bars represent the 95% CI.

3.5 Influence of movement features

As we can see in figure 10, there is a similar pattern in the influence of intensity variation as previously: the recognition ratio drops linearly with the degree of intensity variation, and the other factors like listening condition, movement continuity or pattern complexity may reduce the recognition but as a constant factor to the intensity variation influence.

Figure 10: Mean recognition score for the rhythm patterns considering only the loudspeaker listening: results are grouped by movement continuity type and the degree of sound intensity variation. The scale spans from 1 (100% recognition) down to 0 (0% recognition) and the error bars represent the 95% CI.

3.6 Influence of pattern complexity

As displayed in figure 10, movement continuity has a stronger influence on the groups listening to more complex patterns (musician group) and to analyze the exact influence of rhythmic pattern complexity, we performed a

series of Chi-square tests on the recognition frequency depending on the sound types. The results show that for the audiovisual group (simple rhythmic patterns) there is a significantly lower recognition rate for the accelerated pattern, which is more complex than the regular pattern. For the musician listeners, two groups clearly appear: the complex patterns (duple and triple metered patterns) have a significant lower recognition rate ($p < 0,001$) than the simple patterns (regular and accelerated).

Figure 11 displays the recognition scores for the different rhythm patterns, with the significant differences circled out.

Figure 11: Mean recognition score for the rhythm patterns considering only the loudspeaker listening: results are grouped by pattern type. The scale spans from 1 (100% recognition) down to 0 (0% recognition) and the error bars represent the 95% CI. Results are grouped according to significant differences (chi-square test).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The most salient result of our experiments is that temporal variability is the most influential factor from the parameters we have introduced. This is essential, as either in audiovisual sound (a car moving, people walking...) or in music (electro-acoustic or mixed instrumental), sounds do vary in time, and we never encountered the completely stable synthetic sounds that are used in most experiments of sound spatial perception. For music purposes, most experiments are missing the crucial point by eliminating temporal variability.

The recognition rate is very low for the conditions that are closer to real music or audiovisual sound, i.e. loudspeaker listening of sounds with time variability that evolve continuously, recognition rate drops below 30% (see figure 10), even if we have only 4 possible patterns that are known before hand, and that they are heard alone, without coinciding sounds as we would have in a music or audiovisual work. Considering that we have an oversimplified listening task compared to real conditions, the recognition rate lets us conclude that spatial trajectories

are not suited as a music language parameter with patterns that may be recognized by the audience.

Another result is that musical training does not improve spatial trajectories recognition, maybe considering that this is not a usual musical task. In our case, non-musicians had even better results than musicians, due to the simpler sound stimuli they had to rate. A broad study on the reception of Western music features showed that some musical capacities are acquired through exposure to music without the help of explicit training. These capacities reach such a degree of sophistication that they enable untrained listeners to respond to music as “musically experienced listeners” do [1]. These results are extended to an area more close to rhythm, perception of timing, where judgments are not so much influenced by expertise levels, but by exposure to a certain musical idiom. “As such, the current study provides evidence for the idea that some musical capabilities are acquired through mere exposure to music, and that these abilities are more likely enhanced by active listening (exposure) than by formal musical training (expertise)”[8]. Also, we can see that for the most restrictive task, that is, the synthetic stable stimuli, with simple patterns, the recognition can be superior to 90% and even close to 100% when the sounds do not evolve continuously. There is a clear rhythmic pattern in this case, but this would be achieved more simply with any amplitude variation.

Sound spectral features (harmonics-to-noise ratio, pitch, spectral width) play a residual role compared with temporal intensity variations, whereas experiments that use only stable sounds tend to describe the influence of these features as the most significant [3].

Finally, the listening condition had a lower influence than expected: there was a significant improvement in recognition with headphones as opposed to loudspeakers, but this difference was less important than the influence of sound temporal features. Furthermore, the position of the listener in the room or the separation of the loudspeakers did not have a clear influence on recognition, therefore, when dealing with relatively complex sounds, the composer or sound designer can guess the recognition of the sound movement patterns by the audience, even if a particular listener is not located in the perfect spot (in stereo or surround configurations). That is to say, provided that the composer or sound-designer really pay attention to what can be heard and not heard in spatial movement.

More importantly for musical applications, when listeners were informally asked about their subjective evaluation, they predominantly explained that, even if they could mentally recognize some rhythmic patterns, it was an abstract mental effort of trying to match the spatial trajectory of a given sound with one of the rhythmic patterns, and it was very different from the feeling of recognizing rhythm of changing notes that will emerge as an intuitive musical pattern. “The ability to analyze surface patterns of pitch, attack, duration, timbre in a refined way is probably less important than the ability to integrate all of these features in a structured whole. Without an integrative stage of processing, this perceptual ability, as refined as it may be, would not have any strong implication for musical experience.” [8]

Spatial movement patterns should therefore be restricted to sonification tasks where the sound is perfectly stable in time, and the patterns are very simple, possibly imitating feasible sound trajectories found in nature like the regular pendulum movement or the acceleration that can occur with a bouncing object.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was partially supported by the project PAID-06-07-3301 funded by Universidad Politécnic de Valencia, and the project GVPRE/2008/377 funded by Generalitat Valenciana, Conselleria d'Educació.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] E. Bigand and B. Poulin-Charronnat. “Are we ‘experienced listeners’? A review of the musical capacities that do not depend on formal musical training.” *Cognition*, Vol. 100, pp.100–130, 2006.
- [2] J. Blauert: *Spatial Hearing, the Psychophysics of Human Sound Localization*, MIT press, Cambridge MA, USA, 1997.
- [3] D.S. Brungart and B.D. Simpson: “Effects of temporal fine structure on the localization of broadband sounds: potential implications for the design of spatial audio displays,” in *Proc. 14th Intl. Conf. Auditory Display*, Paris, France, June 24-27, 2008.
- [4] L. Campesato: “A Metamorphosis of the Muses: Referential and contextual aspects in sound art,” *Organised Sound*, Vol. 14, No. 1, pp. 27–37, 2009.
- [5] C.I. Cheng and G.H. Wakefield: “Moving Sound Source Synthesis for Binaural Electroacoustic Music Using Interpolated Head-Related Transfer Functions (HRTFs),” *Computer Music Journal*, Vol. 25, No. 4, pp. 57–80, 2001.
- [6] M. Chion: *Audio-Vision: Sound on Screen*, Columbia UP, New York, 1994.
- [7] *GRMtools. Freeze specification* (retrieved april 2010) <http://www.grmtools.org/qt/files/Freeze.html>
- [8] H. Honing and O. Ladinig: “Exposure Influences Expressive Timing Judgments in Music”, *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, Vol. 35, No 1, pp. 281–288, 2009.
- [9] P. Schaeffer: *Traité des objets musicaux, 2nd edn.*, Editions du Seuil, Paris, France, 1977.
- [10] M. Trochimeczyk: “From Circles to Nets: On the Signification of Spatial Sound Imagery in New Music,” *Computer Music Journal*, Vol. 25, No. 4, pp. 39–56, 2001.
- [11] I. Xenakis: *Formalized music*, Indiana University Press, Bloomington, USA, 1971.
- [12] V. Zouhar, R. Lorenz, T. Musil, J. Zmölnig and R. Höldrich: “Hearing Varèse’s Poème électronique inside a virtual Philips Pavilion,” in *Proc. Intl. Conf. Auditory Display (ICAD 05)*, Limerick, Ireland, 2005.